

AN EXPLORATORY STUDY OF LEXICO-SYNTACTIC VARIATIONS IN SAMBALPURI AND ODISIA*

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Abstract

This paper attempts to identify the changes that are found at the levels of lexis and syntax within Sambalpuri and Odia. This study explores how the structures of syntax and lexicon change from one geographical area to another. In doing so, the study attempts at bringing out the different lexical and syntactic phenomena from the morpho-syntactic perspective. Under the morphology section, it throws light on case endings, pluralisation, classifiers, post-positions, honorifics, emphatic particles and spatio-temporal nouns or frequentative adverbs agglutinating with various categories. Under the section of syntax, the paper gives adequate emphasis on copular verbs, negation and serial verbs.

[Keywords: Odia, Sambalpuri, Lexical variation, Syntactic variation, Morpho-syntactic]

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1. Introduction

Languages vary concerning how the information structure of an expression is encoded. Etymological methods for stamping information structure incorporate word order and morphology at the syntactic level. Odia and Sambalpuri are alluringly superseding languages where information structuring is used by the utilization of lexico-syntactic variation. Apparently, all speakers of one language can talk and understand to one another at a large extent. Yet, no two of them speak identically. The differences persist because of age, sex, social circumstance, and where and when the language was learned. Thus, the distinctions are reflected in the choices of word, pronunciation, grammatical rules and so on. Every speaker speaks at least one language or variety just as each individual, an idiolect. A language does have different varieties or closely related other languages. One language or variety is not inferior or superior to the other and logically cannot be so.

Odia [ISO 639-3: “ori/ory”]¹ became the first language in India on the basis of a state formed, known as Utkal (now Odisha) and was carved out of different Provinces in 1936 (see detail in Pattanayak & Prusty, 2013: Chapter-1). Though it may seem to the outside world that the people of Odisha speak one language i.e., Odia, the state has many varieties of Odia and dialects which are so distinct from each other in terms of grammar, lexicon and syntax that they lead to the communication breakdown. Some of the varieties of Odia spoken across the state of Odisha are standard Odia, Berhampuri (Southern Odia), Baleswari (Northern Odia) and

¹ [<https://www.ethnologue.com/language/ory/17>] and [https://www.ethnologue.com/15/show_language/ori/]

Note: In each instance, the first correspond to Sambalpuri marked with (spv) whereas the second denoted to Odia as (ori) or otherwise stated aside.

Sambalpuri [ISO 639-3 “spv”]² (Western Odia) etc. It is a common phenomenon in Odisha that the people speaking standard variety find it quite difficult to understand when they meet people speaking other varieties of Odia across Odisha. At the same time, all varieties are written in common Odia script despite their variations.

In the *Linguistic Survey of India*, Sir George Abraham Grierson (1928: 368-9) had vociferously averred that there are no dialects of Odia within its geographical area. Moreover, scholars such as Goloka Bihari Dhall (1959), Kunja Bihari Tripathi (1962) and Mahapatra et al. (2002: ix) have stated that there exist some dialects for Odia³. However, whether Sambalpuri is an independent language or not has been a controversial question (see Biswal, 2010). Some people call Sambalpuri as hyphenated Kosali [Kosli/Koshali], which has been noticed these days in use. Until now, in the Indian Census, there is no language called Koshali in Odisha but return of Sambalpuri does have in record (see e.g. Mahapatra et al. 2002: 9-10). Similarly, Sambalpuri, getting the status of an independent language and constitutional status has become a political issue rather than a linguistic one as Patel (2002: 2) and many others have remarked. In addition, there are so many varieties of Odia, such as Baleswari, Ganjami and so on. These dialects have the linguistic influences from the dominant languages of the adjacent regions. For instance, Baleswari has some linguistic influences from the Indo-Aryan language, Bengali; Ganjami has impacts from the Dravidian language, Telugu. On the contrary, Sambalpuri language has effects from the Indo-Aryan languages like Chattisgarhi, Bagheli, Bundeli, Bhojpuri etc., while Odia standard language is influenced by the Odia variety spoken in the eastern Odisha (see Dasgupta, 1964; Patel, 2002: 39). Indo-Aryan languages

² [<https://www.ethnologue.com/language/spv>]

³ [http://www.ciil-lisindia.net/oriya/Oriya_vari.html]

2. (ori)⁵ *gopa:lɔ* *gotie* *bɔɾɔ* *kəkʰa:ru* *ha:tɔ-ru* *a:ɲila: ni/na:hĩ*
 Gopal-3MSG.NOM one-CLF big pumpkin market-LOC bring-
 3SG.PST.PFV NEG

‘Gopal did not bring a big pumpkin from the market.’

In the above two examples, between Sambalpuri and Odia, we can observe the differences at two levels: syntax and lexicon. As far as syntax is concerned, in Sambalpuri, the negation */na:ĩ/* precedes the main verb */a:nla:/* whereas in Odia, */-ni/* or */na:hĩ/* follows the main verb */a:ɲila:/*. In addition, negation in Sambalpuri is a free morpheme whereas in Odia, both free and bound forms exist. As far as the lexicon is concerned, Sambalpuri and Odia have two different words */ma:kʰan/* and */kəkʰa:ru/* for ‘pumpkin’, respectively. Furthermore, there are other differences too that can be seen. For instance, to convey the meanings, “one” and “big”, Sambalpuri has words like */gutel/* and */baɾʰel/* respectively. Similarly, the standard Odia has */gotiel/* and */bɔɾɔɔ/*. Though */gutel/* and */gotiel/*, and */baɾʰel/* and */bɔɾɔɔ/* have some degree of similarity in sounds, yet the clear distinction in pronunciation of these groups of words cannot be unnoticed.

2. Lexical Features

As far as the morphology is concerned Sambalpuri has three kinds of words: those having similarity with Odia, partially different from Odia and totally different from Odia⁶. Mathai (2013) has pointed out that varieties such as Sambalpuri, Bargarhi, Sundergarhi have 75-76% lexical similarity with the standard variety of Odia.

⁵ This paper follows IPA transcription and Leipzig glossing rules, see Grammatical Acronyms Table in *Appendix*.

⁶ [http://www.ciil-lisindia.net/oriya/Oriya_vari.html]

However, this may not be fully correct as there are variables of data collection such as the region, word list, the age of the speakers and so on. In another study, Behera & Dash (2017) have shown the lexical similarity is of 52.46% score between Sambalpuri and Odia. Below tabulated words are completely different from Odia (see Table 1).

Sambalpuri (spv)	English	Odia (ori)
<i>teŋʈa:</i>	Chameleon	<i>enḍuə</i>
<i>nard̥iba:</i>	To run	<i>d̥ouʈiba:</i>
<i>ic^hni</i>	Now	<i>ebe</i>
<i>kunḍa:</i>	Dumb	<i>mukə</i>
<i>b^haēra:</i>	Deaf	<i>bəḍ^hirə</i>
<i>uil</i>	Onion	<i>piə:ʝə</i>
<i>ma:ɛʝ^hi</i>	woman	<i>məhiʎa:</i>
<i>kul^hia:</i>	Jackal	<i>bilua:</i>
<i>ʝ^haṭ</i>	Quick	<i>sig^hrə</i>
<i>mɛc^ha</i>	Moustache	<i>nisə</i>
<i>jun^ha:</i>	Old	<i>puruṇa:</i>
<i>sā:kur</i>	Narrow	<i>əprəsəʝṭə</i>
<i>ʝ^huri</i>	Small fish	<i>c^hoṭəma:c^hə</i>

Table 1: Lexical Variations between Sambalpuri and Odia

Under the main sub-section of ‘agglutination’ vs. ‘inflection’, ‘case endings’, ‘pluralisation’, ‘classifiers’, ‘post-positions’, ‘honorifics’, ‘emphatic particles’ and ‘spatio-temporal nouns’ or ‘frequentative adverbs’ are discussed vividly.

2.1 Agglutination vs. Inflection

According to Vance (1987), “[In agglutinating languages] each morph represents only one semantic unit... The other property is that morphs are simply stuck together (‘agglutinated’); ideally, the boundaries between morphs are clear, and there is no allomorphy.” Again, “an agglutinating language is a language in which words are made up of a linear sequence of distinct morphemes and each component of meaning is represented by its own morpheme”⁷ (see also Bickford & Daly, 1996; *SIL International*, 2004).

Emeneau (1965) has emphasized on the system of numeral classifiers during his initial consideration of India as a ‘linguistic area’. Barz & Diller (1983) also concur with Emeneau in this respect. The motivation to study this aspect has been drawn from Haspelmath (2009), where he has stated that languages can be both agglutinating in nominal morphology and inflectional in verbal morphology in a befitting reply to the established Agglutination Hypothesis that an X language is “agglutinating/fusional in one area of morphology (in nouns or in the future tense), it tends to show the same type elsewhere”. Further, Greenberg (1954 [1960]:182) has also averred the fact that a language can both be agglutinating and inflecting at the same time. Wolfgang U. Dressler (1985) along Skalička’s lines (cited in Pöchtrager et al., 1998) has also acknowledged that “noun inflection and verb inflection may have a different typological character within the same language and

⁷ <https://glossary.sil.org/term/agglutinative-language>

develop diachronically in typologically different directions” (see Dressler, 2005:7).

Mohapatra & Hembram (2010: 206-7) have opined that Odia is a “morphologically an agglutinating language.” Furthermore, in Odia, “the suffixes, post-positions, and case endings agglutinate with the verbs, nouns, adverbs or pronouns: also one or more suffixes can combine with the base word” (see also Dash, 1982; Jena et al., 2011: 125). Behera (2015 & 2016) and Behera et al. (2018) have also asserted the fact that some areas of Odia and Sambalpuri are agglutinating. One of the reasons that could be ascribed to this unique phenomenon is the territorial belt where these languages are spoken. Both these languages are spoken in a belt encircled by the Indo-Aryan languages on the Eastern, Northern and Northwestern sides and the Dravidian languages on the other side, the southern part. That is why, Odia is considered as a “typologically disturbed language”, as stated by Patnaik (2003), because it has assimilated both the features from the Indo-Aryan and Dravidian families.

In the following illustrations the first one refers to Sambalpuri (#3i & #4i) which is followed by Odia (#3ii & #4ii) and they will exemplify the assimilation of features both from Indo-Aryan and from Dravidian.

3. (i) *ma:s t̪ar-ma:n-kar-nu*
(teacher+plural+hon.gen+location/ablation)
- (ii) *f̪kʰɔkɔ-ma:n-ɔnkɔ-tʰu:ru*
(teacher+plural+hon.gen.oblique+location/ablative/locative case)
‘from the teachers’
4. (i) *i-gu t̪a:ka-r-nu*
(this+plural+gen+ablative case)
‘from these’
- (ii) *ei-gu t̪ikɔ-tʰu:ru*
(this+plural+ablative case)
‘from these’

2.1.1 Case Endings

2.1.1.1 Nominative Case

Like most of the Indian languages nominative case has a default covert marker for both Sambalpuri (# 5) and Odia (#6).

5. *muĩ* *ma:cʰte* *kʰa-emi*
 I-1SG.NOM fish-CLF eat-1SG.IMP.FUT
 ‘I will eat fish.’

6. *mũ* *ma:cʰɔ tie* *kʰa:-ibi*
 I-1SG.NOM fish-CLF eat-1SG.IMP.FUT
 ‘I will eat fish.’

2.1.1.2 Accusative Case

For Sambalpuri (#7) the accusative marker is /-ke/ whereas the counterpart (#8) has /-ku/. For instance,

7. *ra:m* *ra:ban-ke* *ma:r-le*
 Ram-3MSG.NOM Raban-ACC kill-3SG.PFV.PST.HON
 ‘Ram killed Ravan.’

8. *ra:mɔ* *ra:bɔŋɔ-ku* *ma:r-ile*
 Ram-3MSG.NOM Raban-ACC kill-3SG.PFV.PST.HON
 ‘Ram killed Ravan.’

2.1.1.3 Dative Case

Here one must differentiate between the dative subject experiencer and the dative object beneficiary. However, the respective dative markers such as /-ke/ for Sambalpuri (#9) and /-ku/ for Odia (#10) are used for both the dative subject and beneficiary.

9. *hari* *maɖʰu-ke* *bahi-te* *ɖela:*
 Hari-3MSG.NOM Madhu-DAT book-CLF give-3SG.PFV.PST
 ‘Hari gave a book to Madhu.’

10. *həri mɔɖʱu-ku bɔhi-tie ɖela:*
 Hari-3MSG.NOM Madhu-DAT book-CLF give-3SG.PFV.PST
 ‘Hari gave a book to Madhu.’

However, the dative subject experiencer in Sambalpuri (#11) also takes the ending /-ke/ in a contrast to the latter language (#12).

11. *mɔte (to me) pa:n na:ĩ bʱul lage⁸* (Sahu, 2011)
 I-DAT.SUB betel-3SG NEG good feel-3SG.IMP.PRS
 ‘I do not like betel.’

12. *mote (to me) pa:nɔ bʱɔɔ la:ge na:hĩ*
 I-DAT.SUB betel-3.SG good feel-3SG.IMP.PRS NEG
 ‘I do not like betel.’

2.1.1.4 Locative Case

Location is marked by four case ending markers such as /-e/, /-re/, /-na/, /-ne/ and /-nu/ in Sambalpuri (#13) whereas Odia (#14) has markers like /-re/, /-ru/, /-ɖei/.

13. *ɖame iskul-na ɖhila ka:ẽ?*
 You-2SG.NOM.HON school-LOC be-2SG.IMP.PST.HON why
 ‘Were you in school?’

14. *ɖume skul-re ɖʱilɔ ki?*
 You-2SG.NOM.HON school-LOC be-2SG.IMP.PST.HON why
 ‘Were you in school?’

(Pattanayak & Dash, 1972)

2.1.1.5 Ablative Case

Ablation refers to the separation of an entity or a being from the other one. It is marked by endings such as /-nu/, /-u/ and

⁸ [<https://koslisahitya.wordpress.com/2011/09/17/kosli-a-distinct-language/>]

/-tʰa:nu/ in Sambalpuri (#15) and /-ru/ and /-tʰu:ru/ in Odia (#16). For instance,

15. *gacʰnu paʃar-te ʃʰuʃucʰe*
 tree-ABL. leaf-3SG.NOM.CLF fall-3SG.PROG.PRS.
 ‘A leaf is falling from the tree.’

16. *gacʰru paʃra-tie ʃʰuʃucʰi*
 tree-ABL. leaf-3SG.NOM.CLF fall-3SG.PROG.PRS.
 ‘A leaf is falling from the tree.’

2.1.1.6 Instrumental Case

It is marked by postposition such as /dʱwara/ for both varieties. The marker /-tʰi/ is used along with the instrument to supplement cutting as in the following instance in Sambalpuri (#17) when Odia (#18) uses /sɔʃiʃɔ/ or /-re/.

17. *rahim sabʃi-guʃa:-ku caku-tʰi ka:tsi*
 Rahim-3MSG.NOM vegetables-ACC knife-INST cut-3SG.IMP.PRS
 ‘Rahim cuts vegetables with the knife.’

18. *rahim pɔriba:-guʃi-ku cʰuri-re ka:te*
 Rahim-3MSG.NOM vegetables-ACC knife-INST cut-3SG.IMP.PRS
 ‘Rahim cuts vegetables with the knife.’

2.1.1.7 Vocative Case

The markers such as /re/, /a:re/, /habe/, /haere/, /haelo/, /hago/, /haeho/ and many others are mostly used as vocatives in Sambalpuri (e.g. #19) whereas /he/, /hoihe/, /are/, /ho/, /hoire/, /hoilo/, /heiti/, /hoigo/, /hoiho/, /a:be/ and a few others are frequently addressed as vocatives for Odia (e.g. #20). The markers such as /hago/, /hoihe/ and /heiti/ are used for endearing vocation for husbands by their wives. The forms such as /haeho/, /hoihe/ are used for friends whereas /halo/ and /hoilo/ are used to address the

Behera, 2015; Behera, 2016; Behera et al., 2016; Behera, 2017; Ojha et al., 2015; Jena et al., 2011). The classifiers such as /-ʃʰan/ and /-ʈa:/ are used for human generic countable and non-human generic countable nouns respectively. While the standard variety counterparts like /-ʃʌŋʌ/ and /-ʈi/ are also referents of the human generic countable and non-human generic countable nouns.

- | | |
|------------------------|--------------|
| 25. <i>ca:r-jʰan</i> | <i>lok</i> |
| Four-CLF | men |
| 26. <i>cha:ri-jaŋʌ</i> | <i>lokʌ</i> |
| Four-CLF | men |
| ‘four men’ | |
| 27. <i>ca:r-ʈa</i> | <i>gacʰ</i> |
| four-CLF | trees |
| 28. <i>ca:r-ʈi</i> | <i>gʌcʰʌ</i> |
| four-CLF | trees |
| ‘four trees’ | |

2.1.4. Post-positions

Some of the post-positional markers in Sambalpuri are /*lekʰe*/, /*a:gru*/, /*saŋe*/, /*a:ga ru*/, /*ʈak*/ etc. On the other hand, their counterparts in Odia are /*bʰʌʃi*/, /*purbʌru*/, /*sʌhʌ*/, /*a:gʌ:ru*/, /*pʌrʃʌŋʌ*/ respectively. There could be some more post-positional divergences between Sambalpuri (#29) and Odia (#30) as exemplified.

- | | | | | |
|-------------------------------|-------------|--------------|----------------|-------------------------|
| 29. <i>muĩ</i> | <i>ʈa:r</i> | <i>lekʰe</i> | <i>sa:t-te</i> | <i>pindʰicʰe</i> |
| I-1SG.NOM | him | like | shirt-CLF | wear-1SG.PFV.PRS |
| ‘I have worn shirt like him.’ | | | | |
| 30. <i>mũ</i> | <i>ʈa:</i> | <i>bʰʌʃi</i> | <i>sa:rt</i> | <i>kʰʌnde pindʰicʰi</i> |
| I-1SG.NOM | him | like | shirt | CLF wear-1SG.PFV.PRS |
| ‘I have worn shirt like him.’ | | | | |

2.1.5 Honorifics

The lexical distinctiveness between the two varieties with regard to honorifics is the pronouns and their verbal inflections. The pronouns such as /*tame*/ and /*a:pan*/ in Sambalpuri have their Odia counterparts such as /*tume*/ and /*a:pənɔ*/ respectively. Analogously, the inflections corresponding to both of the above-stated honorific pronouns are mentioned below (Table 3) in a detailed manner in all the tenses and aspects.

Tenses	Forms	Sambal-puri	Odia	Sambal puri	Odia	Sambal-puri	Odia
	verb 'do'	Non-honorific (you)		Honorific 1 (you)		Honorific 2 (you)	
		<i>tui</i>	<i>tu</i>	<i>tame</i>	<i>tume</i>	<i>a:pan</i>	<i>a:pənɔ</i>
Present	Imperfective	<i>kar-su</i>	<i>kər-u</i>	<i>kar-sa</i>	<i>kər-ɔ</i>	<i>kar-san</i>	<i>kər-ən̩ti</i>
	Progressive	<i>kar-u-cu</i>	<i>kər-u-ɔh̩</i>	<i>kar-u-ca</i>	<i>kar-u-ɔh̩</i>	<i>kar-u-can</i>	<i>kər-u-ɔh̩n̩ti</i>
	Perfective	<i>kar-i-cu</i>	<i>kər-i-ɔh̩</i>	<i>kar-i-cʰɔ</i>	<i>kər-i-ɔh̩</i>	<i>kar-i-chan</i>	<i>kər-i-ɔh̩n̩ti</i>
Past	Imperfective	<i>kar-lu</i>	<i>kər-i-lu</i>	<i>kar-la</i>	<i>kər-ila</i>	<i>kar-le</i>	<i>kər-ile</i>
	Progressive	<i>kar-u-t̪ʰlu</i>	<i>kər-u-t̪ʰlu</i>	<i>kar-u-t̪ʰila</i>	<i>kər-u-t̪ʰila</i>	<i>kar-u-t̪ʰile</i>	<i>kər-u-t̪ʰile</i>
	Perfective	<i>kar-i-t̪ʰlu</i>	<i>kər-i-t̪ʰlu</i>	<i>kar-i-t̪ʰila</i>	<i>kər-i-t̪ʰila</i>	<i>kar-i-t̪ʰile</i>	<i>kər-i-t̪ʰile</i>
Future	Imperfective	<i>kar-bu</i>	<i>kər-ibu</i>	<i>kar-ba</i>	<i>kər-iba</i>	<i>kar-be</i>	<i>kər-ibe</i>
	Progressive	<i>kar-u-t̪ʰibu</i>	<i>kər-u-t̪ʰibu</i>	<i>kar-u-t̪ʰiba</i>	<i>kər-u-t̪ʰiba</i>	<i>kar-u-t̪ʰibe</i>	<i>kər-u-t̪ʰibe</i>
	Perfective	<i>kar-i-t̪ʰibu</i>	<i>kər-i-t̪ʰibu</i>	<i>kar-i-t̪ʰiba</i>	<i>kər-i-t̪ʰiba</i>	<i>kar-i-t̪ʰibe</i>	<i>kər-i-t̪ʰibe</i>

Table 3. Honorific Systems in Sambalpuri and the Standard Odia

2.1.6 Emphatic Particles

Many lexical forms are used for emphasis during verbal communication in both the varieties. The morphological particles used for emphasis are /-bʰi/, /-bi/, /-tɑ/ for both Sambalpuri (#31) and Odia (e.g. #32) with a slight change /-bi/ for the latter.

31 *muĩ* *ina* *bʰi* *kʰa:emi*
 I-1SG.NOM here EMPH eat-1SG.IMP.FUT
 ‘I will eat here also.’

32 *mũ* *eʰʰa:re* *bi* *kʰa:ibi*
 I-1SG.NOM here EMPH eat-1SG.IMP.FUT
 ‘I will eat here also.’

2.1.7 Spatio-temporal or Frequentative Adverbials

Spatio-temporal nouns in Sambalpuri such as /*ina*/, /*senɑ*/ (#33), /*harmisa:*/, /*iaʰke*/, /*sea:*ʰke/ and so on are morphologically quite different from their standard variety counterparts such as /*eʰʰare*/, /*setʰare*/ (#34), /*sɔrbɔda*/, /*eiaʰɔku*/, /*seiaʰɔku*/ etc., respectively.

33. *pila:-ma:ne* *senɑ* *kʰelucʰan*
 boys-3PL.NOM. there play-3PL.PROG.PRS
 ‘Boys are playing there.’

34. *pila:-ma:ne* *setʰa:re* *kʰelucʰɔŋʰi*
 boys-3PL.NOM. there play-3PL.PROG.PRS
 ‘Boys are playing there.’

3. Syntactic Features

In this section, distinctive features pertaining to syntax have been taken into consideration. The whole section, hereunder, has been categorized into three subsections: the use of copular verbs, negation and serial verb constructions.

3.1 The Use of Copular Verbs

“A copular verb is an intransitivity which links the subject to the noun phrase, adjective and other constituents which express the predicate”⁹ (see. e.g. Hartmann & Stork, 1972; *SIL International*, 2004).

Copular verbs as independent verbs in a verb phrase are one of the salient features of Sambalpuri which is very similar to Hindi. On the contrary, as far as the standard variety is concerned the usage of copula is optional¹⁰. The morphological forms such as /a:e/ and /æ'ɛ/ in Sambalpuri and /ɔ'te/ and /æ't/ in the standard variety are the copular verbs which can be exemplified in the following sub-sections.

3.1.1 Connecting Nominal Heads (subject or object) with Predicates

Another interesting point is that copulas such as /a:e/ and /ɔ'te/ in Sambalpuri (#35) and the standard variety (#36) respectively are used to relate the nominal head or objects with the predicates.

35. *muĩ* *gu te* *b'al* *pila:* *a:e*
 I-1SG.NOM one-CLF good boy be-IMP.PRS.COP
 ‘I am a good boy.’

36. *mũ* *go tie* *b'ɔ'ɔ* *pila:* *ɔ'te*
 I-1SG.NOM one-CLF good boy be-IMP.PRS.COP
 ‘I am a good boy.’

⁹ [<https://glossary.sil.org/term/copula>]

¹⁰ CIIL sources on “*Language Variation in Sambalpuri: A Dialect of Oriya*” [http://www.ciil-lisindia.net/oriya/Oriya_vari.html]

3.1.2 Connecting Predicative Adjectives with Predicates

Contrarily, verbs like /ɔc^hẽ/ (#37) and /ac^hi/ (#38) are used to relate the predicative adjective with the predicates of the sentence which can be more obvious with the following instantiated examples.

37. *muĩ* *b^hal* *ac^hẽ*
 I-1SG.NOM good be-1SG.IMP.PRS.COP
 ‘I am fine.’

38. *mũ* *b^hɔɔ* *ɔc^hi* (Pattanayak & Dash, 1972)
 I-1SG.NOM good be-1SG.IMP.PRS.COP
 ‘I am fine.’

3.1.3.1 Non-honorific or Informal

39. *ɬui* *guɬe* *b^hal* *pila:* *a:e* (spv)
 You-non-honorific one-CLF good boy be-2SG.IPFV.PRS.COP
 ‘You are a good boy.’

40. *ɬu* *goɬie* *b^hɔɔ* *pila:* *ɔɬu* (ori)
 You-non-honorific one-CLF good boy be-2SG.IPFV.PRS.COP
 ‘You are a good boy.’

3.1.3.2 Honorific 1

41. *ɬame* *guɬe* *b^hal* *pila:* *a:a* (spv)
 You-honorific one-CLF good boy be-2SG.IMP.PRS.HON.COP
 ‘You are a good boy.’

42. *ɬume* *goɬie* *b^hɔɔ* *pila:* *ɔɬɔ* (ori)
 You-honorific one-CLF good boy be-2SG.IMP.PRS.HON.COP
 ‘You are a good boy.’

(Pattanayak & Dash, 1972)

3.1.3.3 *Honorific 2*

43. *a:pan/a:paŋ gute bʰul pila: a:n* (spv)
 you-honorific one-CLF good boy be-2SG.IMP.PRS.HON.COP
 ‘You are a good boy.’

44. *a:pŋɔ go tie bʰɔɔ pila: ɔ tɔŋɪl* (ori)
 you-honorific one-CLF good boy be-2SG.IMP.PRS.HON.COP
 ‘You are a good boy.’

3.2 Negation (in Verb Phrase)

3.2.1 Pre-verbal or Post-verbal

Negation in Sambalpuri (#45) is a pre-verbal phenomenon while in the standard Odia (#46), it is post-verbal although both of the varieties are not subjected to syntactic scrambling of negation¹¹.

45. *muĩ am na:ĩ kʰu:ẽ*
 SUB OBJ NEG VB
 I-NOM mango no eat-1SG.IPFV.PRS
 ‘I don’t eat mango.’

46. *mũ a:mbɔ kʰu:eni/na:hĩ* (Pattanayak & Dash, 1972)
 SUB OBJ VB+NEG
 I-NOM mango eat+no-1SG.IPFV.PRS
 ‘I don’t eat mango.’

¹¹ *Note:* When we state pre-verbal or post-verbal, it refers to the main verb and not the auxiliary one. Dependent morph such as /-nɔ/ is used between the main and auxiliary verbs in the standard Odia or probably not true with Sambalpuri at least.

3.2.2 Scrambling of Negation

If the word orders for both the languages are reversed from their canonical parametric position, the construction becomes ungrammatical and unacceptable.

47. **muĩ a:m kʉ:ẽ na:ĩ* (spv)
 SUB OBJ VB NEG
 ‘I don’t eat mango.’

48. **mĩ a:mbɔ ni/na:hĩ kʉ:e* (ori)
 SUB OBJ NEG VB
 ‘I don’t eat mango.’

3.2.3 Participialized Constructions

Analogously, the usage of negation in Sambalpuri is furthermore pre-verbal with regard to the participialized constructions (e.g. Sridevi & Choudhary, 2001) whereas in the latter, it is post-verbal.

49. *na:ĩ a:siŋʈiba:r lok-ke ka:ŋa ka:hebe* (spv)
 NEG come-PRS.PFV.PTCP man-ACC what say-
 2SG.IPFV.FUT.HON
 ‘What would you say to the man who has not come?’

50. *a:si-nɔʈiba: lokɔ-ku kɔŋɔ kɔhibe* (ori)
 come-NEG-PRS.PFV. PTCP man-ACC what say-2SG. IPFV. FUT.
 HON
 ‘What would you say to the man who has not come?’

3.2.4 Dependent and Independent Morphs

In addition, it can be used both as a dependent and independent morph in standard Odia which is not available in the case of Sambalpuri. It has only independent morphs or words as negative constructions. Further, in the standard variety, the negative morpheme /-nɔ/ (as in §3.2.3) is used between the main and the

auxiliary verbs within the same morphological unit which is a dependent morph variation of the negative morpheme /*nahĩ*/.

3.2.5 Copular Counterpart

The negation counterparts of copula (see in §§3.1.2) are a unique phenomenon, for they occupy the same position when replaced with copulas. In addition, they are also inflected for honorifics mandatorily in the standard variety (#51) which is optional for Sambalpuri (#52).

51. *a:paŋ/a:paŋ guṭe bʰal pila: nuhe/nuhan*
 you-honorific one-CLF good boy be-2SG..IPFV.PRS.HON.COP
 ‘You are a good boy.’

52. *a:pŋŋ goṭie bʰaŋŋ pila: nuhŋŋi*
 you-honorific one-CLF good boy be-2SG.IPFV.PRS.HON.COP
 ‘You are a good boy.’

3.3 Serial Verbs Construction

It is a common phenomenon that Serial Verb Constructions (SVCs) are considered to have their origin from the paratactic constructions (see e.g. Payne, 1985: 25-7; Foley & Olson, 1985; Andrews & Manning, 1999 for similar discussions). The relation between coordination and verb serialization appears to be quite obvious for VP chaining in most of the Indo-Aryan languages, as in Odia, where a set of verb phrases describes the series of consecutive events (e.g. Beermann & Hellan, 2002; Jha et al., 2014). Analogously, Sambalpuri (#53) too has the contiguous construction where a series of actions can be serialized by addition of a conjunctive participle *-/kari/* coordinating all of them.

53. *ha:t̪ ḍʱuĩ-kari bʰu:t̪ kʰa:i-kari muĩ iskol-ke gali*
 hand washed-CVB rice eaten-CVB I-1SG.NOM school-PP go-
 1SG.PFV.PST
 ‘Having washed my hand and eaten rice, I went to school.’

54. *ha:tɔ dʰoi bʰa:tɔ kʰa:i mĩ skul-ku gɔli*

Hand washed rice eaten I-1SG.NOM school-PP go-1SG.PFV.PST
 ‘Having washed my hand and eaten rice, I went to school.’

(Beermann & Hellan, 2002)

4. Conclusion

Summing up, the introductory section explains about the motivations and rationale for this current study. The second section focuses on the introduction about the languages at hand and their linguistic differences. The third section (lexical features) of this paper contains four sub-sections such as agglutination versus inflection, honorifics, emphatic particles and Spatio-temporal or Frequentative Adverbials. The first subsection sheds much light on the distinctive features between both the languages in relation to the agglutinating features such as case endings, classifiers, pluralization and post-positions. Secondly, the following section lays stress on the differences pertaining to the formation of honorifics. The third part discusses the emphatic particles and their usage in the concerned varieties. Finally, some distinctive features with reference to spatial and temporal nouns including frequentative adverbials have been given due contemplation. In the fourth section, distinctive features pertaining to syntax have been taken into consideration. The whole section has been categorized into three subsections: the use of copular verbs, negation and serial verb constructions. Under the head of copular verbs copulas connecting nominal heads and predicative adjectives with the predicates and copular honorific agreement have been discussed in detail. Similarly, under the sub-head of negation in verb phrase the order of the negation (pre or post-verbal), scrambling, participialized constructions, independent and dependent morphs and copular counterparts of negation have been pondered upon. However, the above-explained discussions are not exhaustive; there may be some more distinctive features between these varieties. One of the future endeavours would be to investigate into the phonetic and phonological differences between both the

varieties. In addition, our investigation would be to figure out the agglutinating nature in the morphology of the other Eastern Indo-Aryan languages, as we have observed in this study that Sambalpuri and Odia have partial agglutinating morphology.

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Appendix

List of Grammatical Acronyms					
First person	1	Focus	FOC	Nominative	NOM
Second person	2	Feminine	F	Object	OBJ
Third person	3	Future	FUT	Participle	PTCP
Ablative	ABL	Genitive	GEN	Particle	PTL
Accusative	ACC	Honorific	HON	Past	PST
Augmentative	AUG	Imperative	IMP	Perfect	PRF
Benefactive	BEN	Imperfective	IPFV	Perfective	PFV
Classifier	CLF	Indicative	IND	Present	PRS
Conditional	COND	Infinitive	INF	Progressive	PROG
Copula	COP	Instrumental	INS	Reflexive	REFL
Converb	CVB	Interrogative	INTERR	Stative	STAT
Dative	DAT	Intransitive	INTR	Singular	SG
Direct	DIR	Linker	LK	Subject	SUB
Emphatic	EMPH	Locative	LOC	Transitive	TR
Evidential	EVID	Negation	NEG	Verb	VB

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